

CHILDREN'S CINEMA UZBEKISTAN: STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This study is devoted to the stages of development of children's cinema in Uzbekistan. Uzbek children's cinema was birth in 1935 with the film "Klich" directed by Yuldash Agzamov. The later, famous cinema director Kamil Yarmatov made contribution for further development of the children's cinema. New era of cinema tography had been started in the 1960 s with young, poetic wave the cinema directors are graduated the Soviet Union Institute of Cinematography.*

On the new stage of the independence period uzbek children's cinema pay to attention to the new generation of directors and new frends created in the cinematography.

Keywords: *cinema, director, movie fairy tale, frame, image, genre, frend, tradition.*

INTRODUCTION. The foundation of Uzbek children's cinematography was laid with director Yoldosh Azamov's film "*Qilich*" (The Sword), created in 1935. Until then, he was known to audiences primarily as an actor. In 1926, children's film director Olga Preobrazhenskaya invited Yoldosh Azamov then a rabfak (workers' faculty) student in Leningrad to play the role of Ali in the film "*Anya.*" Later, he studied at the State Institute of Cinematography in Moscow. He participated in Nabi Ganiev's "*Yuksalish*" (Rise) and Yu. Raizman's "*The Earth is Thirsty*" (*Zemlya Jajdet, Vostokfilm*). From the 1930s onward, Yoldosh Azamov began working as a film director.

"...After the emergence of Uzbek feature cinematography, the People's Commissariat for Education (Narkompros) of the republic raised the issue of creating a feature film for children." [1] The film "*Qilich*" was created by order and under the "consultation" of Narkompros and was classified as an "educational-technical and artistic film."

"*Qilich* is my first completed feature film aimed at children. This was the studio's first attempt at a children's topic. I worked on *Qilich* for five months. My task was to show how the son of a kolkhoz worker becomes interested in technology and to explore the theme of polytechnic education in schools," wrote director Yoldosh Azamov in the January 25, 1935 edition of *Pravda Vostoka* newspaper. [2]

Qilich was Yoldosh Azamov's first work in directing a feature film. The film reflects the theme and politics of its time—preparing technical specialists—through the story of a preschool-aged child's fascination with technology, shown in a silent film format. One distinctive feature of this film was that, for the first time in the studio's history, a child appeared as the main character, and the world was viewed through the child's eyes. The boy's dreams involving a locomotive, his curiosity about technology, his eagerness to discover new things, and his resolution to become a train driver were all presented in ways appropriate to a child's age and behavior. The director's achievement lies in his ability to capture the child's natural and sincere presence in front of the

camera at a time when there was no prior experience in this area—demonstrating his deep understanding of child psychology.

Looking at this film today, we may notice its flaws, such as the idealized portrayal of the socialist system and collective farming, the depiction of a “prosperous and cultured life of kolkhoz workers,” and a “model kindergarten”—all part of a mythologized world. However, *Qilich* remains recognized as the first children's film ever made in Uzbekistan, 90 years ago.

For a long time, *Qilich* remained the only children’s film produced in Uzbek cinematography. The negative effects of the cult of personality, the brutal repression of national creative professionals, and the outbreak of World War II delayed the development of the nascent Uzbek children’s cinematography by several years.

In the late 1940s and early 1950s, the overall decline in the production of feature films across the former Soviet Union, the transformation of the “Soyuzdetfilm” studio into the M. Gorky Film Studio, and the dominance of the “theory of conflictlessness” and “low production” also negatively affected the creation of children’s films. In 1950, only one children's film was produced across the entire Soviet Union, and in 1951, not a single film for the younger generation was made. Finally, in 1952, a turning point occurred in children's cinema, and four children's films were released. One of these was the fairy tale film “*Pakhtakoy*” (*Cotton Princess*), created at the “Uzbekfilm” studio (script by V. Vitkovich and M. Karyukov, directed by Kamil Yormatov, 1952).

The history of the creation of “*Pakhtakoy*” is as follows: the studio’s cameraman M. Karyukov came up with an interesting plot for a modern fairy tale film. The idea was promising, but neither the screenwriter nor the cameraman Karyukov knew how to visualize it on screen. Although the screenwriter V. Vitkovich adapted the concept into a complete literary script, the problem still wasn’t fully resolved. For this reason, the film originally intended to be shot by a Moscow-based director did not achieve its intended goals. The studio found itself in a difficult situation. Such a setback during the stagnant post-war years could have had a negative impact on “Uzbekfilm’s” future operations. At this critical moment, the studio’s artistic director, Kamil Yormatov, took it upon himself to direct “*Pakhtakoy*,” realizing the need to save the studio and its team from crisis.

This experienced artist, deeply aware of the great responsibility placed upon him, did not enter the world of children’s films suddenly or blindly. He thoroughly studied children's behavior, interests, and how they internalize the continuity of real-life events. He sought to adapt serious ideas into a form children could understand. Yormatov was fascinated by the fairy tale genre’s potential the way it opens vast space for imagination and fantasy. In “*Pakhtakoy*,” the characters are divided into “good” and “evil,” “white” and “black,” and the magical element a cotton seed only comes to the hero’s aid in the most difficult moments, based on the hero’s behavior, honesty, and bravery. In this, the creators drew on the traditions of folk tales.

METHODOLOGY. In the early 1950s, the limited development of scientific and technical progress made it difficult to produce technically complex films involving fantastical elements. The core idea of the film was to present, in a fairy tale format, scientific facts about the benefits of cotton—once called “white gold”—for humans, what raw materials are derived from it, and the fight against its pests. Despite the underdeveloped cinematographic tools of the time, the small size of the studio, and general poverty and hardship, the immense responsibility pushed the creators toward “cinematographic innovations.” Indeed, in “*Pakhtakoy*,” not a single one of

the 500 frames was filmed simply every finished frame involved the combination of various events and characters, and each sequence was a combination of two or three shots.

At the time, central press reviews noted that “*Pakhtakoy*” opened a new genre in feature cinematography—fairy tales blending fantasy and real life. “The authors of this new film managed to vividly portray the richness and diversity of a physical world object that young viewers encounter daily, without disrupting the dynamics of the fairy tale plot. The discoveries made by the director and cinematographer in creating an authentic fairy-tale atmosphere through visual effects also captivated children.” [3]

The renowned Komil Yormatov, who brought international recognition to Uzbek cinema with masterpieces like “*Alisher Navoi*,” turned to children’s themes for the first time—and this film also brought him great success.

In 1957, the adventure-detective genre film “*The Desert Incident*” (*Sahrodagi voqea*, script by O. Bondarenko and N. Bondarenko, directed by Z. Sobitov) was produced at the “Uzbekfilm” studio for young audiences.

According to the film’s plot, an unexpected event occurs during a youth glider competition: a powerful typhoon sweeps the glider “*Oygul*” and its crewchildren into a remote desert. Since the main characters are children, the director focused on their performance. Scenes like the children trudging knee-deep in sand under the scorching sun, enduring sandstorms that sting their eyes, and climbing down wells in search of water all were portrayed realistically. Eventually, they come across some people in a ruined building who claim to be archaeologists but turn out to be saboteurs who had secretly crossed the border...

However, “*The Desert Incident*” failed to achieve success with audiences. The main issue was the implausibility of entrusting the task of exposing secret enemy agents, who had infiltrated the country to unarmed children who themselves needed help. The notion that the enemy was captured solely through the strength, intelligence, and resourcefulness of the children seemed unbelievable. Although the director focused on giving the film an adventure-detective appearance, he could not conceal the shallowness of the script. In this film, the “children’s avant-gardism” seen in Soviet children's cinema of the 1920s reappeared.

In the 1960s, political changes and a more relaxed atmosphere helped revive the best traditions of cinema and opened up new creative opportunities. Around the same time, global cinematic innovations, trends, and breakthroughs began to reach Uzbek cinema as well. This period marked a new era in Uzbek children's cinematography. It was characterized by the emergence of young creators with their own themes and styles, and by a broader and more complete use of cinematic possibilities on screen.

On one hand, feature films were influenced by documentary filmmaking; on the other, a poetic approach began to shape the creation of films, elevating children's and youth cinema in Uzbekistan. The pioneers of this new direction were directors like Damir Salimov, Elyor Eshmukhamedov, and screenwriter Odelsha Agishev artists who had just transitioned to independent creative work and wanted to revisit their own childhoods and youth through the lens of contemporary reality. They entered cinematography with their own styles and managed to depict the joyful yet complex world of childhood, its mischievousness, everyday experiences, and nature, through a poetic lens revealing beauty on screen.

“*Olmos*” (*Diamond*, written and directed by Damir Salimov, 1966) can be considered an observational film. Nature is one of the central components of the film and is elevated to an artistic

metaphor reflecting the interconnectedness of humans and nature. The protagonist of “*Olmos*” is a boy named Marat, around 7 years old. His grandfather tends to hundreds of horses on the kolkhoz (collective farm), grazing them across vast plains, meadows, and along babbling streams. Marat often accompanies his grandfather and develops a deep love for the beauty of nature and all living creatures. He becomes especially attached to a horse born before his eyes, nicknamed “Olmos.” However, evil forces destroy this friendship by taking the now-racing-ready Olmos away to compete in horse races.

The theme of understanding children and childhood, treating them with love, and protecting them from cruelty and injustice was first addressed in director Damir Salimov’s film. The poetic style found vivid expression in the film “*Nafosat*” (*Grace*, script by Odelsha Agishev, directed by Elyor Eshmukhamedov, 1967), which introduced the motif of the canal into Eshmukhamedov’s creative world. The director saw sincerity and poetry in the everyday lives of adolescents, on the threshold of adulthood, in harmony with nature, expressed through their simple behaviors and natural expressions. This theme, especially in the “Sanjar” novella, found a vibrant and poetic portrayal of childhood and nature.

During the scorching summer days, Sanjar, like all the other children, swims in the canal, sings, and jokes around. The sequence of balloons, then children, jumping into the water one after another, droplets splashing up and falling back down, kids peacefully floating on balloons along the canal's current, joyful songs, and alternating slow and fast shots—all combine to create a beautiful rhythm of life. Suddenly, the elegant figure of a girl standing by the canal catches his eye, and this marks the end of childhood's carefree world and awakens the first spark of love in the heart of a young boy.

Another significant trend in 1960s Uzbek cinematography was documentary realism. Director Shukhrat Abbasov’s feature film “*You Are Not an Orphan*” (*Sen yetim emassan*, script by Rahmat Fayzi, directed by Sh. Abbasov, 1962) was based on factual events and became one of the earliest films on the topic of World War II. It tells the story of Shoahmad Shomahmudov, a blacksmith in Tashkent, and his wife Bahri Akramova, who took in and raised 14 children of various ages evacuated to Uzbekistan after losing their parents during the harshest years of the war.

Such compassion, kindness, and humanity—traits typical of the Uzbek people were mirrored by many families, which is why the film's characters were made more symbolic, and names were changed. Although the film carried serious thought and social meaning, its driving force was the children. The noble qualities of Mahkam aka and Fotima opa are reflected in how they individually approach each child, treat them with pedagogical sensitivity, and respect their human dignity. This allowed for the creation of richly nuanced child characters.

Beginning with “*You Are Not an Orphan*,” efforts began to uncover new facets of a child's personality, inner world, and psychology. Films like this affirmed that life means love for people, and love is the most noble feeling in the world one that elevates a person spiritually and helps overcome the greatest hardships. “The life-likeness of the material, the artistic believability of the characters and events in ‘*You Are Not an Orphan*’ blend with social generalization and a deep interpretation of the theme of humanism...” [4].

In the 1970s, the poetic direction in Uzbek children's cinema continued in a new form, and new tendencies began to emerge. On screen appeared adult characters who understood children and teenagers, supported their initiative and aspirations, and gave them encouragement during

difficult times. These were the characters of Abbas Gozievich (“*The Mountains Call*”), Anvar’s father (“*These Brave Children at the Car Race*”), Aydar og’a (“*Swallows Fly in the Spring*”), and Grandma (“*The Bitter Pit*”). These characters carried on the legacy of Mahkam aka and Fotima opa (“*You Are Not an Orphan*”), who served as role models in child-rearing.

These films also raised issues related to the spiritual and moral upbringing of the younger generation, and the relationship between nature and humanity. The idea that the foundation of the best human qualities must be laid in childhood was promoted not through moralizing, but through artistic storytelling. This theme was especially vividly expressed in the cinematic novellas “*Swallows Fly in the Spring*” (script by M. Qoriyev and Kh. Akhmar, directed by Kh. Akhmar, 1974) and the film “*The Bitter Pit*” (script by Ya. Filippov, directed by Q. Kamolova, 1975).

In the film “*The Bitter Pit*”, the poetic style is enriched with gentle lyricism, elements of mythical fairy tales, and deep drama. This was the artistic debut of director Qamara Kamolova in feature cinematography, and through the clash of various characters, the film emotionally and movingly narrates the birth of a personality in an adolescent. The creators observe the world of children with a sharp eye, exploring the spiritual life of teenagers, artistically generalizing it, and linking moral and ethical issues to human relationships with nature.

“*The Bitter Pit*” continues the tradition of films in Uzbek children's cinematography that explore the theme of humanity and nature, while also approaching it in a new way. The film teaches the "alphabet of life" step by step, showing that for a person to grow up spiritually rich and morally mature from a young age, such education is equally important in all times. Its educational value remains significant across generations.

The theme of morality is also continued in Kamolova's next film, “*Will You Come Out Tomorrow?*” (*Ertaga chiqasanmi?*, script by K. Lozinsky, directed by Q. Kamolova, 1980). This time, she conducts a sincere and engaging “dialogue” with her youngest viewers, exploring the friendship between a boy and a girl, their mutual respect, their willingness to support each other, and the value of true friendship.

In the 1980s, the theme of relationships between adults and children in Uzbek children's cinema was further explored through the school setting. This topic is raised in films like “*Someone Else’s ‘A’ Grade*” (*Ozganing ‘besh’ bahosi*, script by V. Malinovskaya, directed by G. Bzarov, 1982) and “*Lessons of Tomorrow*” (*Ertangi kun saboqlari*, script by Murod Muhammad Dust, directed by Ahror Akbarkhojaev, 1983), where the focus is on the relationship between students and teachers.

In “*Lessons of Tomorrow*,” Muzaffar Samadiy, a young man who graduates from university in the city, returns to his home village of Ghalatepa to work as a physics teacher. He voluntarily takes on the most difficult class in the school 7th grade class “B” a group notorious throughout the village for their unruly behavior. Even the most experienced teachers had refused to manage them. His decision surprises everyone.

At first, the students test the seemingly quiet, modest, and patient Samadiy’s limits. But he never complains to the principal, nor does he summon their parents. Without delivering lectures or scolding them, he wins their hearts with kindness, sincerity, and by finding a path to each child’s soul. His attitude toward life and his sense of justice have a positive influence on the students, awakening in them a respect for others and a sense of responsibility.

The director successfully portrays the friendship, unity, and empathy between teacher and students. Indeed, for a teenager, having an adult friend who understands, supports, and guides them in the right direction is a true blessing.

In the 1980s, the theme of World War II was revisited in Uzbek children's cinema. While in the 1960s, films on this subject were based on documentary facts, now the events of that period were brought to the screen by directors who were witnesses to those events. These directors, whose childhood coincided with the war years and who had witnessed all the hardships within Uzbekistan, brought those memories of war to life. Some examples include "Leningraders, My Dear Orphans" (screenplay and director: Damir Salimov, 1980), "My Dear Muscovites" (screenplay and director: Khoji Akhmar, 1981), and "The Small Person in the Great War" (screenplay and director: Shuhrat Abbosov, 1989). This important theme, approached from a humanitarian and civic perspective, becomes a generalization that turns into the thoughts and ideas of thousands of viewers when it reaches an artistic level. In this regard, Damir Salimov's artistic film "Leningraders, My Dear Orphans" deserves attention.

The years of World War II coincided with the director's childhood. Despite Uzbekistan being far from the front lines, the director personally witnessed all the difficulties that the people faced, and these experiences remained in his childhood memories. That is why these difficult years are elevated to the level of documentary on the screen. "During the war years, Uzbekistan accepted one hundred thousand children evacuated from places near the front, including Leningrad. Of these, 48,000 children were placed in children's homes, and 52,000 found shelter in Uzbek families."

By carefully studying this period, the director sought out women who had worked directly with children during the war years and had been in charge of children's homes, talking with them. Finally, the image of Khadicha Botirovna, created in Uzbek cinema, stands as a monument to the women who not only empathized with the pain of many children but also found the inner strength to support them, encourage them, and give them hope for the future.

The war brings with it grief, anguish, and worries that a child's fragile heart cannot bear or comprehend. This is expressed powerfully in the repeated words "Oyi, oyi" (mother) in the film. These words are imbued with different emotional tones: sometimes in pity for a mother who has collapsed from cold and hunger, sometimes in fear and desperation during bomb explosions, seeking protection, and at times in a motherly tone, as if calling to comfort. Ultimately, the film highlights the warmth, labor, noble heart, and courage of the Uzbek woman who took care of children of various nationalities.

The director, Damir Salimov, explored different intonations and tones in the words to bring out dramatic effect. In doing so, he continued the tradition begun by Shuhrat Abbosov's film "You Are Not an Orphan" while giving it a new, fresh approach.

The film "*The Small Person in the Great War*" by film director Shuhrat Abbosov is also based on autobiographical facts. As he brings to life the memories of the war and his experiences as a teenager on screen, he looks back at those difficult years through the eyes of a mature person, reflecting on them thoughtfully. The film shows how the war's impact spread to distant regions of the country, capturing the atmosphere of the time and the hardships of life through the fate of a young person. Having endured the hardships, misfortunes, and cruelties of war, meeting different people, and being tempered through life's trials, the character Safo transforms from a dreamy,

trusting boy into a strong-willed, truthful, compassionate person who does not forgive betrayal or wickedness.

Although time swiftly carries us away from the years of World War II and the horrifying consequences it brought to humanity, the painful memories and the scars it left in our hearts can never be washed away. Conveying the courage of the people who protected the homeland from destruction and saved the future, especially to the younger generation, is part of the struggle to ensure that those terrible years are never repeated.

On September 1, 1991, Uzbekistan gained independence in its historical, social, and economic development and entered a new phase. This new era required a completely new national cinema, one that was in line with the country's national mentality, reflecting its traditions, values, and customs, and requiring a new subject, style, and principles. During the independence period, new creative forces in Uzbek children's cinema began their work, rejecting the Soviet-era model and aesthetic canons. They embraced the new period of renewal, exploring new subjects and styles, shedding light on the contradictions of life, revealing the human spirit, and creating national character.

A deeper approach to nationalism and the creation of national characters led filmmakers to turn to the traditional village life where ancient values were still preserved. In this regard, the national spirit, national character, and traditions that were almost forgotten, along with folk songs that are often sung in play, were revived on the screen and seamlessly integrated into modern themes. The film *"Tangalik Children"* (screenplay by R. Mukhammadjonov, directed by T. Yunusov, 1992) is a good example of this.

In the new era, the search for creating cinematic works that capture the spirit and mood of the times, in line with today's demands, has led to the formation of new trends in Uzbek children's cinema, bringing about a renewal of traditions. During the period of independence, the young creative forces entering the field boldly produced authorial films from the very beginning. The sharpest social ideas, the most urgent topics, serious concepts, and philosophical meanings are conveyed to the audience through distinct forms and styles in an understandable cinematic language. Such a direction, which became known as the "new wave" in Uzbek cinema, began with the work of film director Zulfiqar Musakov. His films *"Abdullajon or Dedicated to Steven Spielberg"* (written by Z. Musakov and R. Mukhammadjonov, directed by Z. Musakov, 1991) and *"The Little Doctor"* (written and directed by Z. Musakov, 1998) present the problems of adults through the image of a child protagonist. In these films, deeply meaningful concepts, serious thoughts, and major issues of the time are conveyed in a clear cinematic language, naturally and sincerely, blending elements of humor, comedy, and fantasy.

In one of the Uzbek villages, an ordinary child, who is no different from human beings, arrives on a flying saucer from another planet. This child, with curly hair and fair skin, appears familiar to the audience. He does not understand the meaning of negative words like "thievery" or "greed," but possesses human virtues in their entirety. He goes to great lengths to help the villagers, easing their difficult lives and making their dreams come true. As a result, fantastic events start occurring in the village: melons and watermelons that are too large to fit in a hug, livestock breeding so well that each one has multiple offspring, and magical sickles, like those from ancient fairy tales, that lighten the villagers' work and immediately transport them to the market. However, the kolkhoz chairman's sickle, due to his "unforgivable sin," can never fly. Although contact with

extraterrestrials is forbidden in the village, an ordinary peasant, Bozorboy, adopts the alien as his son and names him Abdullajon, giving him a hat.

The attempt to bring reality closer and address urgent issues became a unique trend in the new era of Uzbek children's cinema, and this direction continued in the film *"The Little Doctor."* In this modern-themed film, fantastical elements are also introduced. The film's protagonist, a 7-year-old boy named Doniyor, uses all his inner strength to save his mother from a serious illness and protect her from death. As Doniyor begins to believe in his extraordinary power, one day, he brings back the hand of an elderly man who lost it in the war. The fame of the little doctor spreads throughout the entire village, even reaching the city and the wealthy Shodmonov family, whose granddaughter lies unconscious. The little doctor is urgently called for. However, before treating the illness, he must first address a deeper "sickness" in the household, purifying the family from an unhealthy environment, illicit wealth, and selfishness. Although the protagonist is a child, this film highlights various negative societal flaws and the issues troubling the masses. These problems, expressed through different genre elements, are brought to the audience in an engaging and thought-provoking way.

This trend continues in the film *"Tilimoy – The Amazing Girl"* (scriptwriters Anvar Obidjon, Muzrob Boymukhammedov, directed by M. Boymukhammedov, 1999), where the main character is a robot. The film is based on the short story *"The Golden-Hearted Autobot"* by writer Anvar Obidjon. The director doesn't blindly follow the original work, but instead, keeping the unique qualities of cinema in mind, he makes several changes to the script to create a child-friendly, fantasy-filled, and detective-style story. The main character, the golden-hearted autobot, is replaced with a robot girl, Tilimoy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. A distinctive feature of the new era of Uzbek children's cinema is that fantastic or technological characters are presented not in an exotic style or setting, but in familiar conditions and with human-like emotions for the audience. Tilimoy, created by Professor Kamtariy, speaks like a living person, sings, "reads" others' thoughts, and is full of feelings. The film's success lies in its combination of science fiction with detective and comic elements, as well as the integration of songs and music.

In the years of independence, folklore and oral traditions have been adapted to modern times, with their traditions renewed and represented in a way that resonates with contemporary life. The most experienced filmmakers in the field began to explore this genre. For example, one of the most accomplished filmmakers, Jasur Iskhakov, directed his own authorial film. His movie *"Adventures in the Kingdom of Chess"* (scriptwriters J. Iskhakov and M. Iskhakova, directed by J. Iskhakov, 2008) is a modernized fairy tale. It depicts how the rapidly developing technologies and the computer age enhance the intellectual capacity of the younger generation, who begin winning various competitions, intertwining modern-day fantasy with the world of fairy tales. The innovation of the film is that it merges the ancient mind-bending game of chess with modern technology, emphasizing the power of human intelligence and talent.

As Uzbekistan continues to evolve, it has opened up greater opportunities for creativity, and a number of creators have ventured into making authorial films. In this context, the work of scriptwriter Rikhsivoy Mukhammadjonov deserves mention. His film *"The Old Man and His Grandson"* (script and direction by R. Mukhammadjonov, 2008) presents a unique portrayal of a child character.

"The Old Man and His Grandson" is a modern-themed film set in one of the Uzbek villages, encompassing all the internal contradictions of life. Its protagonists are Obid Ata, a man with a strong character who has gone through a tough life, and his seven-year-old grandson, Ganisher. The grandfather is left with three grandchildren to care for, and the moral upbringing of the children continues through him. The youngest grandson especially relies on his grandfather, and they are always together. Although still a child, Ganisher has a well-formed character and is an active participant in all the events and incidents in the family. He is a stubborn and resilient child who fights against injustice in his own way and seeks revenge on those who have wronged him. The scenes involving the child are filled with humor and wit. The director captures the paradoxical way children think at this age. The simultaneous occurrence of funny, sad, and dramatic events in one moment provides a broad representation of life.

"Grandfather and Granddaughter" – On one hand, it is a film tailored for young audiences. In it, tragic and dramatic events are portrayed through certain details and national customs, while on the other hand, it reflects on life and human issues using the example of a family, presenting moral traditions and philosophical ideas that will not leave adult viewers indifferent.

"Oyjion" (screenplay by Z. Musokov and B. Odilov, 2001) confirmed the authors' unique ability to work with young children. Created in collaboration with Japanese filmmakers, this film portrays the inner perspective of a five or six-year-old girl named Narziz, who is deprived of her mother's affection. Narziz lives with her father and grandmother but frequently visits her deceased mother's grave, and a sequence shows the suffering of a childless woman in faraway Japan. Slowly, the film transitions into human emotions, showing how two nations with different languages and cultures find a connection.

Every day, Narziz, the daughter of an artist, brings food to her father in Registon Square. By chance, she sees a woman from Japan, who resembles her deceased mother, and Narziz believes this woman is her mother. In fact, the woman looks exactly like the one in the photo Narziz holds... Through the lens of good intentions, noble dreams, and human virtues, the fantasy of a pure, sincere, imaginative Uzbek girl helps to unite the people of the two nations. This film is emotionally narrated. In the 21st century, the exploration of the spirit, inner world, and aspirations of young people continues in Uzbek children's cinema through films like **"Oydinoy"** by director Nozim Abbasov, **"Don't Forget Me"** by Kamara Kamolova, and short films like **"Speech"** and **"Zoo"** by M. Abdukhaliqov. Kamolova, who has created many films for both children and adults, in her film **"Don't Forget Me"** focuses on the most responsible moments of childhood. The film emphasizes how the formation of a person during this period is connected to their relationship with their land, nature, compassion for animals, and other virtues, all shaped by the upbringing received in childhood.

The upbringing of young people has always been a relevant task throughout history. In the second half of the 19th century, the great Russian writer Leo Tolstoy saw school education and reading books as one of the key tools for the upbringing of the younger generation. He opened a school in Yasnaya Polyana and taught, writing small stories for children. "For centuries, the wisest people have strived to raise human beings who are rational, insightful, spiritually beautiful, hardworking, and virtuous." [6]. However, for many years, topics such as school education, teacher-student relationships, and moral-educational issues, which are the foundation for youth education, were often overlooked by filmmakers. The interest in reading books, writing, and exploring the world around us begins early in childhood. It is essential not to extinguish this

interest. In Nozim Abbasov's "**Oydiyoy**" (2008), the main character is a six-year-old girl. The film artistically explores the interest and inner aspirations of six-year-olds to study, suggesting that this noble feeling should be recognized and supported at the right time.

"**Oydiyoy**" is not accepted into the first grade because she is too young. Still, the diligent girl, eager to learn how to write and read, dreams of growing up quickly and every morning carries her bag full of books and notebooks, rushing to school alongside the other students. However, in the film, the child's yearning to learn faces several obstacles as she begins her journey into life...

Although time changes and life moves forward, a child remains a child in every era pure of heart, in need of help, and full of emotions. If someone supports the child and contributes to shaping their personality, it is a blessing. In this film, the delicate phase where the foundation of a human being is formed is explored, and the image of adults who protect childhood is continued in a new form and content. The film "**Oydiyoy**" is a typological variant of the 1980 film "**Alpamis Goes to School**" (director A. Karsakboev, 1980), made by the "**Kazakhfilm**" studio. This theme continues in 21st-century Uzbek cinema, showing that the moral and intellectual upbringing of young generations, the development of a well-rounded person, is an important task in every era.

In the new era, the integration of school education with moral, cultural, and national traditions is becoming an essential life necessity. The 2021 film "**School is My Life**" (screenplay by N. Abboskhon, directed by I. Mukhammadibrohimov), produced by the "**Kozgu**" studio under the commission of the Uzbekistan Cinema Agency, seriously explores this topic, boldly addressing life's challenges. It highlights the fact that the future is determined by the education and upbringing of today's students, and their fate starts from the first place of learning. Shaping a child or adolescent's personality, bringing out their inner potential, and guiding their abilities is a high responsibility shared by parents, teachers, and educators.

In "**School is My Life**," the film's content and essence revolve around two different approaches to students' education and upbringing. The film's main character is the school principal, Rakhmatov, who has many years of experience in pedagogy. He advocates for reaching the hearts of children and adolescents and nurturing them with love. On the other hand, Sharipov, sent by the district department of public education, believes in establishing "iron discipline" in the school. Rahmatov does not argue or debate with his opponent. Instead, through his active efforts to unite the teaching staff and students and to value the importance of educators, he leaves Sharipov speechless. In the end, Sharipov acknowledges that children also need love.

Human character is complex. Finding a way into the heart of an adolescent and having a positive influence on them, being just, responsible, and demanding is a difficult task. This raises the question of what the main criterion is for an adolescent's development. First and foremost, it is the teacher's love, kindness, and belief in their students. As the great thinker Alisher Navoi said, "Politeness cultivates humanity in a person's nature, and as a result, love for people is born in human nature" [7]. Such thoughts about humanity and love for people are relevant in all eras.

As for the creative forces of present-day Uzbekistan, their search for a unique way to create cinema that aligns with the new era is noteworthy. The explorations of young filmmakers such as Umid Hamdamov, Sarvar Karimov, Nozim Jumayev, and Akbar Bekturdiyev, who tackle topics that resonate with the spirit of the times, are undoubtedly positive. However, regarding the 21st century generation, one might ask whether their cultural-aesthetic and moral-educational upbringing is keeping up with the times, social progress, dynamic changes, and the speed of life. In this new era, cinema holds a crucial place in shaping a perfect generation. However, it is

concerning that this field is often neglected by creators, with films dedicated to the younger generation being produced sporadically and their educational potential not being given enough attention. Now that Uzbek cinema has garnered attention and been elevated to the level of state policy, it is only fair that young viewers demand films that are ideologically deep and artistically mature.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be said that the development of Uzbek children's cinema and its evolution into an independent art form owes a great deal to the creative work of Yuldosh Azamov, Komil Yormatov, and Shukhrat Abbosov, who supported this field and laid its foundation. Later, the traditions initiated by these great artists continued in the works of directors such as Khoji Akhmar, Damir Salimov, Muxtor Og'amirzaev, and Muzrob Boymukhamedov. The films raised issues related to nature and human problems, moral-ethical education, and the relationship between students and teachers. Most importantly, the films reflected the life, dreams, hopes, and aspirations of the youth of their time in artistic imagery.

In the years of independence, Uzbek children's cinema turned towards realism, with new generation creators exploring topics, plots, and characters that are in harmony with the spirit of the times. It should be noted that it is unfortunate that the most influential artistic opportunities in producing a perfect generation that meets the demands of tomorrow are not being used effectively, and regular production of films for young viewers has not been established. In today's era of advanced technology, it is only natural that the responsibility of creating a well-rounded generation that suits our fast-paced life is placed on the shoulders of the filmmakers.

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